

Going up against the Challenges of Consumer Behavior in Indian Market through Dynamic Retailing

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Abstract

A fundamental understanding of consumer behaviour underpins all shopping activity and is a required prerequisite to organizations being selling orientated and thus profitable. Most products eventually end up in individual households even though they will reach through several steps on their way from producer to end-user. Traders and producers form vertical chains or networks, called value chains, at the end of which are the consumer. Understanding consumer behaviour is not only crucial for the generator but all the other actors in the chain. The price that the consumer puts on the services or goods limits what everyone else can get from the worth chain. Most purchases are made to satisfy the problem. Analysis of problem attention can be done through the ‘means-end’ chain concepts. This looks at what drives a consumer to buy stocks. The search for the message can be either internal or external; the latter can also be either active or passive. Consumers usually have several alternative solutions to choose from and, depending upon the complexity of the shopping, will each be multi-attribute decision-making or based on choice heuristics. Results tend to depend upon the degree to which performance meets expectations which in turn can be influenced by several factors within and outside the marketer’s control.

Keywords – Consumer Behavior, Marketing, Retailing, Value Chains.

Profits from customer relationships are the primary aspect of all business. So the basic intention of any business is profit maximization through client satisfaction. But it is always hard to get customer satisfaction. A consumer may state his needs and wants and yet may act otherwise. The consumer may not be aware of his deeper motivations and may change his mind at any stage. In spite of such diversities among consumers, there are many similarities among them. To find these, the study of target customers wants; perceptions and shopping and purchasing behaviour will be helpful as it will give the information necessary for developing new products, prices, channels communication and other shopping components. In the majority of sales, however, buyers differ enormously in terms of their buying dynamics. The task faced by the marketing strategist in coming to terms with these differences is complex. In consumer markets, for example, not only do buyers typically differ in terms of

their age, income, educational levels and geographical location, but more fundamentally in terms of their personality, their lifestyles and their expectations.

Consumer durables are facing more competition from different brands as competition in an industry is growing up day by day. Retail chain outlets shop owners need to concentrate on every aspect of their activities, uniquely “Brand Image” because it is the main factor that it can influence the customer in their buying process. A company can lead the market only when its products are allowed by the customers. This can be made possible by understanding the requirements of the consumers. Many types of research attempted to know the current position of consumer durables in the market and to identify the market Leader, Challenger and defender in retail chain outlets market. Customer retention and customer retention selling are key components in managing a profitable business. The aim of customer retention marketing is to convert first-time or occasional buyers into loyal, long term customers. To accomplish this, a company needs to get the requirements of its business consumers.

Dealers play a vital role in converting the occasional or first-time buyer into a loyal customer. The level of satisfaction attained by the dealers by the competitor products should also be understood to improve the quality of the current products. Understanding Consumer behaviour is a very important factor for business success. Consumer behaviour is a rapidly growing field of research and teaching, which, in addition to the considerable value of others and marketing managers who are professionally concerned with buying action. An important reason for studying consumer behaviour is the evaluation of consumer groups with unsatisfied needs and desires. The essence of the latest marketing notion is that all parts of the business should be organised for the satisfaction of consumers. The challenge to the marketers is to determine the relative influence of the various factors and to apply and adapt skillfully the so-called information to a proper shopping mix. In other terms, the total marketing effort must be so composed that the consumer notices its different features as providing an answer to his recognised problems and felt needs. Consumer analysis seeks to determine the underlying currents and cross-currents in the consumer’s minds. It focuses on the causes rather than the results of effective marketing strategy and tactics employed by the firms that are successful in the markets. This is a necessary process which has a vital role in consumer behaviour study.

In most states, a decision involves the selection of an option from two or more attractive choices. The buying process is the method of decision-making, leading to a purchase function. It represents a problem-solving approach. The mechanism is the same as in any processing activity in which we supply some input followed by the processing activity and finally, the output comes before us. During the last two decades, numerous models of consumer behaviour depicting the buying process have been developed. All these models treat the consumer as a decision-maker who comes to the market area to answer his consumption problems and to achieve the achievement of his needs. The simple model given is composed of three stages—‘Input Process and Output’. Input is a stimulus. It is provided by two sets of stimulus variables, namely, the firm’s marketing efforts and the social environment. The firm’s marketing efforts are designed to positively expose, inform and influence consumers. These efforts include product/service itself, advertising, price strategies, distribution network, and all marketing function.

When a company introduces a new brand of detergent powder or a video set, it may run a series of radio commercials with supporting press advertisements. The social environment serves as a non-commercial source of consumer information and influence, which is not under the direct control of the firm. It includes a reference which is not under the direct control of the firm. It includes reference groups and individuals, members of the family, social class and castes, culture and like. Both of these stimulus variables influence consumers and the buying process. A subdivision of a national

religion composed of a combination of factorable social situations such as class status, ethnic background, region (rural or urban) and religious affiliation, but forming in their combination of a functioning unit which has an integrated impact on the participating individual. People belonging to a particular subculture although are part of the same culture but still they maintain their identity by possessing distinct beliefs, different ways of doing the same thing which is setting them apart from other subcultural groups. Hence, within the overall complex cultural system, one will find distinct groups, which are distinct because of their distinct subcultures.

The complex cultural system can be segmented into various subcultures based on geographic region, religion, age, gender, social class, economic status, etc., each of these segments is not distinct from each other but is overlapping. For example, based on geographical location, one can broadly divide the Indian culture into North Indian, South India, West India, East Indian. Based on religion, one can divide them into Hindu, Muslim, Christian, Sikh, Jain, Buddhist, etc. based on age one can divide them into very young, teenager, youth, middle-aged and old aged. Some of the overlapping subcultural groups can be a North India teenager who is a Sikh, or a South India middle-aged who is a Christian Roman Catholic, while another old aged South Indian who is a Christian but a Protestant. Similarly, one can talk about a young West India Hindu Brahmin and an old East Indian Sunni Muslim. The list of such overlapping subcultures will just go on. A young teenager whether he is a Hindu or Christian, coming from Calcutta or Chennai may love to wear jeans, visit fast-food restaurants and be a fan of Ricky Martin. Here the guiding factor for the marketer is that the consumer belongs to generation “X” and hence has a more cosmopolitan lifestyle. Out of many subcultures, only some of them are important for the marketer to study for formulating effective marketing strategies.

Conclusion

In general, the following categories of subcultures should be studied by marketers for formulating effective marketing strategies. Age subculture – marketers have been able to use age as an effective basis for identifying various subcultural identities. In general, the market is divided based on age subculture as the youth market, the elderly market besides the various stages of the family life cycle where the purchase activity is very frequently and significant like bachelorhood, honeymooners and parenthood. The youth market is a very important market which includes teenagers, bachelorhood, honeymooners, because of several reasons. Firstly in this segment, there is a tendency to spend a higher proportion of income than in any other stage and consumption pattern formed in this stage tends to remain lifelong. If a young bachelor buys an automobile and is satisfied with it, the chances are that he will come back to the same company if he decides to buy a new automobile later in his life, be it a honeymooner stage or parenthood stage.

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